

AI MARKETING FOR REAL-TIME CUSTOMER SEGMENTATION: AUTOENCODER-ENHANCED TIME-EVOLVING CLUSTERING

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ABSTRACT

Conventional customer segmentation methods often rely on static models that fail to capture dynamic consumer behavior. Consumer behavior is influenced by external factors such as economic shifts, cultural events, and seasonal trends, necessitating an adaptive approach. This study explores AI marketing segmentation as a solution to track and predict consumer state transitions. The research utilizes deep learning-based feature extraction and time-evolving clustering to analyze grocery store transaction data from April to June 2022, covering pre-Ramadan, Ramadan, and post-Ramadan periods in Indonesia. An autoencoder neural network is employed to reduce high-dimensional transaction data into a latent representation, which is then clustered using MiniBatch K-Means to identify evolving customer segments. The study also applies transition analysis to track segment shifts over time. Findings reveal that customer behavior is fluid, with distinct segment transitions occurring in response to Ramadan. The transition analysis highlights that static segmentation models fail to capture these changes. AI-driven marketing segmentation, enables faster tracking of shifting consumer behaviors, allowing businesses to proactively adjust their marketing strategies.

Keywords: *Dynamic Segmentation, Customer Behavior, Clustering, AI Marketing, Deep Learning, Autoencoder*

1. INTRODUCTION

Customer segmentation has always been a key part of marketing. It helps businesses group people based on what they have in common [1]. Companies look at things like age, location, interests, and shopping habits to tailor ads, products, and deals [2]. This makes marketing more personal and keeps customers engaged.

For years, businesses have used the same methods to organize their marketing. A cosmetics brand might sort customers by skin type [3], while an online store separates buyers into frequent shoppers, occasional buyers, and first-time visitors [4]. These approaches help businesses focus their efforts and build stronger relationships. But there's a problem, most of these methods assume people stay the same [5], [6].

Traditional segmentation relies on fixed traits like age, income, or location. While useful, these factors don't capture how people change over time. Traditional market segmentation methods, which focus on fixed traits such as age, gender, and

geography, provide only a partial view of consumer behavior [7]. Even behavioral and psychographic segmentation, which consider habits and lifestyles, often rely on past actions and ignore evolving preferences [8]. Needs-based segmentation aims to adapt but still assumes that people's priorities remain stable unless manually updated. These tools rely on static data, which limits responsiveness to changing needs, highlighting the importance of regular updates to ensure accuracy and effectiveness. [9], [10].

In reality, people change. A budget-conscious shopper might start buying premium brands after a raise. Someone who loves eating out might start cooking at home due to health concerns or a tighter budget. These shifts can be slow or sudden, making fixed segmentation models outdated.

Big events also shape behavior. When the economy slows down, people look for cheaper options. When times are good, they spend more on luxury. Holidays and cultural moments make an even bigger impact [11]. During Ramadan, for example, grocery

shopping changes dramatically as people buy staple foods in bulk. Shopping hours shift too, many prefer late-night or early-morning trips. Businesses that fail to adjust miss out.

Technology speeds up these shifts even more. Online shopping has changed how people buy, shifting habits from stores to digital platforms. Social media can make a product go viral overnight. A skincare brand featured in a trending TikTok might sell out in hours, attracting customers who never considered it before [12]. Without a flexible approach, businesses fall behind, pushing outdated marketing that no longer connects with people [13]. That's why businesses need adaptive segmentation. Unlike fixed models, adaptive segmentation updates automatically, adjusting to changes in habits, preferences, and outside factors. This is especially important for seasonal changes, economic shifts, or viral trends. Traditional models keep targeting people the same way, while an adaptive system sees new trends, like a surge in bulk grocery buying and shifts marketing strategies in real time.

This is where AI marketing makes all the difference. AI-powered segmentation uses machine learning to analyze data instantly, predict shifts, and personalize offers. Unlike traditional methods that need manual updates, AI constantly refines customer groups based on new behaviors [14], [15], [16]. Staying ahead becomes simpler when businesses use predictive analytics, recommendation engines, and automated marketing platforms. These tools refine strategies, improve targeting, and offer more personalized marketing efforts.

AI also enables faster decision-making by cutting down the time it takes to process information and respond to changes. In a traditional setting, spotting a drop in sales or a shift in customer behavior might take days or even weeks of manual analysis. With AI, those signals can be picked up almost instantly. AI tools can also automatically test and deploy personalized offers or pricing strategies without waiting for human input [13], [17], [18].

Traditional segmentation often struggles to keep up with how quickly consumer behavior can change. Demographic, geographic, and behavioral models are still widely used, but they tend to miss abrupt shifts, like those triggered by Ramadan or sudden economic changes. These static methods assume stability, which doesn't reflect how real people shop and respond.

AI-driven adaptive segmentation offers a way around that limitation. Instead of grouping customers based on past traits alone, machine

learning models adjust in real time, responding to new patterns as they happen. Predictive analytics, automated personalization, and dynamic audience clustering allow businesses to update their targeting and messaging more fluidly. As preferences shift, strategies can shift too helping brands stay relevant, connect more meaningfully, and react faster in a market that rarely stands still.

Although customer segmentation has been widely studied, many existing models remain static and struggle to adapt to changing consumer behavior. This limitation is particularly evident in emerging markets such as Indonesia, where cultural events like Ramadan can lead to rapid shifts in purchasing patterns. This study addresses that limitation by introducing a method that tracks behavioral changes over time through deep learning and dynamic clustering. The approach is designed to support more responsive marketing strategies that account for evolving social and economic conditions in retail environments.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Businesses have been sorting customers into groups for years. They look at things like age, shopping habits, and personal interests to tailor marketing. This helps them focus their ads, promotions, and product offerings.

1. Demographic Segmentation

One of the most common methods is grouping people by age, gender, income, and education [19]. The idea is that people with similar backgrounds have similar buying habits. A fashion brand, for example, might market differently to Gen Z than to Baby Boomers [20]. Luxury brands focus on high-income shoppers [21], while budget retailers target lower-income groups [22].

But people are more complex than their demographics. Two people of the same age and income can have completely different lifestyles and spending priorities. As they experience life changes, their preferences shift. That's why static demographic segmentation often falls short.

Next method groups customers based on their actions, how often they buy, what they purchase, and how they engage with a brand [23]. It's widely used in e-commerce, loyalty programs, and streaming services, which recommend content based on past activity. Retailers often segment shoppers like this:

- Frequent buyers get loyalty rewards.

- Occasional shoppers receive special offers to keep them coming back.
- First-time visitors are given discounts to encourage a second purchase.

The downside? It assumes past behavior predicts future behavior. A once-loyal customer might lose interest, but the system keeps treating them as valuable. Meanwhile, new habits might go unnoticed [24], [25]. Without real-time updates, businesses miss chances to engage customers at the right moment.

Another approach is psychographic segmentation, where in this approach digs into what drives people, their values, interests, and personalities. Psychographic segmentation can identify distinct consumer segments based on individual differences such as risk attitudes, cognitive ability, and decision-making styles. For instance, Blömker and Albrecht [26] identified six segments with varying readiness to take risks and decision-making styles, which influence channel choice and switching behavior in a multichannel environment. Brands use this to connect emotionally with customers, aligning marketing with lifestyle choices.

A well-known model, VALS (Values and Lifestyles), sorts people into groups based on motivation, like Innovators or Achievers [27]. While insightful, this method is time-consuming and costly. It requires surveys and continuous updates, or else it becomes outdated [28].

All these methods assume people stay the same. But buying habits shift with economic changes, cultural trends, and seasonal events. A marketing strategy based on last year's data may no longer apply. Businesses relying on static segmentation often miss key opportunities [29]. To keep up, businesses are turning to AI. Machine learning can track shifting behaviors in real time and adjust marketing automatically [30]. Unlike fixed categories, AI models adapt as consumer habits change.

One promising approach is deep learning-based feature extraction. This approach determines which behaviors need attention without doing it manually, artificial intelligence can find hidden patterns from a large transaction data set [31]. With auto encoder Complex data can be made compact and meaningful without manual effort. Conventional approaches to Clustering such as K-means are still useful, but they assume that the shape of the cluster remains consistent over time. [32], [33]. This assumption no

longer applies to the retail business where consumer behavior often changes in response to various promotions, trends or seasonal events such as the Ramadan fast.

A more effective way to divide consumers into segments is by involving time-evolving clustering. Thus a model is needed that can continuously improve, which is certainly more suitable for environments with very rapid changes such as e-commerce., this method captures shifts across defined time windows [34]. Such methods are certainly very useful during seasonal events when buyer behavior tends to change drastically.

This study applies MiniBatchKMeans, a variation that processes data in smaller chunks. Unlike k means in general, this method makes computation lighter without reducing the performance of clustering much.. [35]. This method is particularly useful in environments with large-scale data, thus making this method a scalable clustering method that works with large datasets and adapts to consumer changes. By combining it with deep learning, businesses get a more flexible, real-time view of customer behavior, especially during high-variability periods like Ramadan.

Most segmentation studies still rely on static models that do not adapt to changing consumer behaviors. Even AI-driven approaches typically fall into two categories: rigid segmentation frameworks that lack real-time updates or fully online clustering, which is widely used in e-commerce but rarely applied in grocery retail.

This study addresses these gaps by integrating deep learning to uncover hidden patterns in customer data and time-evolving clustering to track segment shifts over multiple periods. Additionally, it emphasizes short-term behavior changes, enabling businesses to adjust marketing and inventory strategies in real time. By combining AI with adaptive segmentation, this research offers a practical solution for businesses looking to keep pace with dynamic consumer habits.

Most customer segmentation models rely on fixed RFM scores or demographic rules, which limit their ability to reflect changes in behavior over time. In contrast, this study introduces a method that combines deep feature extraction with temporal segmentation to track customer behavior with greater detail and flexibility. By capturing subtle shifts in patterns that are often overlooked by

traditional techniques like market basket analysis or basic K-means clustering, the method offers a more responsive view of customer dynamics. Unlike psychographic approaches such as VALS, it does not depend on ongoing surveys, making it more practical and cost-effective for use in large-scale retail environments.

3. METHOD

3.1. Data Description

This study looks at a grocery store transaction data from April to June 2022 in Indonesia, a period chosen to track buying habits before, during, and after Ramadan. Since Ramadan brings noticeable changes in shopping behavior, it's a great time to study shifting consumer patterns.

To stay efficient without sacrificing key insights, the dataset is limited to the five best-selling products each month. After cleaning and pre-processing the data set used had 13,000 data transactions covering consumer demographics, time of the transaction and various purchasing information. Such data structures make it easy to observe how purchasing behavior changes in response to seasonal patterns and major events.

3.2. Analytical Approach

To understand how consumer segments shift over time, this study applies an AI-based clustering approach that unfolds in three core steps. The first involves feature extraction using a deep learning autoencoder. This model compresses the original high-dimensional transaction data into a simplified format, preserving the essential behavioral signals while removing noise and redundancy. By doing so, the data becomes more manageable and structured for clustering.

Next, MiniBatchKMeans is used to segment customers on a monthly basis. Unlike traditional KMeans, this method processes the data in small batches, which makes it well suited for handling large volumes of retail transactions without excessive computational cost. Finally, customer movement across clusters is tracked month to month. By mapping these transitions, the model reveals how purchasing behavior evolves in response to external influences like seasonal demand, promotional campaigns, or economic shifts. This process not only uncovers emerging patterns but also highlights which groups remain stable and which tend to shift,

offering a more dynamic view of customer segmentation.

3.3. Feature Extraction Using Deep Learning

Business transaction data usually has two types of data, namely numeric and categorical. This makes the Clustering method generally difficult when the number of variables increases. To overcome this problem, an autoencoder can compress the data into a low-dimensional format while still preserving important patterns. It works by learning a compact representation and then reconstructing the original input from it [36]. In this study, an auto encoder is used to reduce the transaction data set into two dimensions of consumer purchasing patterns so that it is easier to group with good accuracy. This event can also help reveal hidden relationships between purchasing patterns and consumer demographics, thereby providing cleaner segmentation than just using raw data.

3.4. Time-Evolving Clustering

After feature extraction, consumers will then be grouped by month to observe how behavior changes over time. The clustering process in this study uses MiniBatchKMeans, which is another type of lighter K-Means that can process data in small pieces, making it more efficient for large data sets. Model evaluation using Silhouette Score, Calinski-Harabasz Index, and Davies-Bouldin Index to determine the optimal amount of clusters. These measures can help determine whether the number of clusters is able to reflect meaningful patterns of behavior [37]. The Clustering process will be repeated continuously for 3 months to track changes in trends and observe how consumer clusters emerge, develop or may be fade.

MiniBatchKMeans updates the clusters incrementally, which makes it more responsive to real-time changes in consumer habits [38]. When paired with autoencoder-based feature reduction, this method supports an AI-driven segmentation framework that adapts smoothly to seasonal cycles.

3.5. Customer Transition Analysis

After clustering has been done, how consumers switch between segments is observed over time. A table mapping the transition of each consumer to the clusters formed for April, May and June is created to show who remains in the group and who is different. These shifts reveal behavioral patterns that static

segmentation tends to miss. When customer segments are treated as fixed, subtle but important changes in how people shop often go unnoticed. A group that once responded well to certain promotions might start favoring different products, or their buying frequency might change around specific events. If these transitions aren't tracked, businesses risk sending offers that no longer resonate, stocking items that no longer match demand, or missing out on moments when customers are most likely to buy.

3.6. Data Preparation

Table 1 shows POS transaction records from store XYZ, including product names, descriptions, transaction dates, quantities sold, and revenue. Each record is linked to a MEMBER_ID, making it possible to track individual customer purchases. For example, customer 1126 appears multiple times, and price differences for Product A hint at possible changes in pricing. The dataset supports analysis of sales patterns, customer habits, and product performance.

Table 1. Raw Data From Store's POS System

ITEM	ITEM DESC	DATE	QT	SALE	ID
A	desc A	16/01	1.00	20,000	1126
B	desc B	10/01	1.00	25,000	1126
C	desc C	23/01	1.00	25,000	1126
A	desc A	29/01	1.00	30,000	1496

Another dataset includes member information with key demographics such as names, gender, age, and unique membership IDs. This data connects customer profiles to transaction history, making it easier to study buying behavior. Merging these demographics with sales records allows customer segmentation by age or gender, supporting more focused marketing and tailored offers.

The process starts by joining transaction data with member details using Member_ID to build a more complete view of purchasing habits. To streamline analysis, only the top five best-selling items each month are included. This keeps the dataset lean while preserving major trends. The data is then reshaped into a pivot table for easier interpretation. To stay within layout limits, the transaction data is shown as sample from complete long table. Table 2 shows each customer's general info and purchase history for the first group of product categories. Table 2b adds more categories, and Table 2c wraps

up the rest. Consists of Member_ID, Age, Gender, Trans_Date, Biscuit, Noodle M, and all of the products available by the store as column. 0 mean the customer did not bought the item and 1 mean they bought the item.

Table 2. Customer & First Set of Products

ID	AGE	GEN DER	TR DATE	Biscuit	Noodle M
1126	48	F	01/04	0	1
1127	41	F	01/04	0	0
1128	46	F	01/04	0	0
1129	40	F	01/04	0	0

After reshaping the dataset into a pivot table, several preprocessing steps followed to get it ready for analysis and modeling. The goal was to extract useful features and organize the structure for segmentation.

Transaction dates (TRANS_DATE) were first converted into proper datetime format using the day/month/year structure. This made it possible to filter by time and run time-based transformations. Only transactions from April, May, and June were kept to narrow the focus to a specific period. A new column labeled TimePeriod grouped entries by month for easier temporal analysis.

To bring in demographic details, gender was encoded numerically, assigning 0 to 'Female' and 1 to 'Male'. Age was binned into four categories, Young, Early Middle, Late Middle, and Old using quantiles. These categories were one-hot encoded into binary columns like AgeCat_Young and AgeCat_EarlyMiddle. The original age group column was dropped to prevent redundancy.

The final dataset combined product basket features, gender codes, and one-hot encoded age categories, setting the stage for clustering and behavioral segmentation

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After preprocessing, the merged transaction and member datasets offered a full view of purchasing patterns by connecting sales records with demographic details. The next step involved identifying major trends and preparing the data for deeper analysis. An Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) followed to uncover insights. The focus was on understanding customer demographics and transaction behavior, laying the groundwork for later modeling and segmentation.

Figure 1. Customers Age Distribution

Figure 1 illustrates the age distribution of customers in the dataset. The histogram shows that the majority of customers fall within the 30 to 50-year-old range, with a peak around the mid-40s. The distribution exhibits a right-skewed pattern, indicating that while most customers are middle-aged, there are also older customers with fewer younger participants.

Figure 2. Customers Gender Distribution

Figure 2 presents the gender distribution of customers. The results indicate a significant imbalance between male and female customers, with female customers forming the majority of the dataset. The number of male customers is considerably lower in comparison.

Figure 3. Number of Transaction

Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of transactions across the 3 months observation. The highest number of transactions occurred in the fourth month, significantly exceeding the transaction counts for the fifth and sixth months. This trend suggests customer activity peaked before the Ramadhan. The decline in transactions in subsequent months could indicate a normalization of purchasing behavior.

The EDA results suggest potential shifts in customer segmentation over time. The age distribution (Figure 1) shows a concentration of customers in their 30s to 50s, while the gender distribution (Figure 2) indicates a dominant female customer base. However, the transaction trends in Figure 3 reveal fluctuations in purchasing activity, hinting at possible seasonal or promotional influences that may attract different customer segments at various times. These patterns suggest that businesses need dynamic segmentation strategies to better target and engage different groups over time.

To reduce dimensionality and extract latent representations of customer purchasing behavior, an autoencoder neural network was implemented. The autoencoder consists of an encoder-decoder architecture, designed to learn a compact feature representation while reconstructing the original input as accurately as possible.

The input layer is defined based on the number of selected features (feature_columns). The encoder consists of two fully connected layers: a hidden layer with 16 neurons and ReLU activation to capture non-linear relationships, followed by a bottleneck layer with 2 neurons and linear activation, representing the low-dimensional latent space. This bottleneck serves as the compressed feature representation of the input data.

The decoder mirrors the encoder, reconstructing the original input from the latent space. It first expands the latent representation using a hidden layer with 16 neurons and ReLU activation, followed by an output layer with the same dimension as the input and sigmoid activation to ensure normalized outputs.

Two models were created:

- The autoencoder model, which maps input features to their reconstruction, allowing for unsupervised learning of compressed representations.
- The encoder model, which extracts the 2D latent representation from the bottleneck layer for downstream clustering or visualization.

The autoencoder was compiled using the Adam optimizer and trained with binary cross-entropy loss, suitable for learning patterns in normalized or binary data. This approach enables effective dimensionality reduction while preserving essential structural information for customer segmentation.

Figure 4 illustrates the training loss curve of the autoencoder model over 50 epochs, with the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss on the y-axis and the number of training epochs on the x-axis. The loss rapidly decreases within the first 10 epochs. As training progresses, the loss continues to decline but at a slower rate, showing a gradual convergence. Around 30 epochs, the loss stabilizes near 0.68 MSE, suggesting that additional training provides minimal improvement.

Figure. 4 Autoencoder Training Loss Curve

Clustering was carried out using an autoencoder for dimensionality reduction, followed by MiniBatch K-Means. For each month April, May, and June transaction data was first normalized using MinMaxScaler to bring all feature values into the

same range. A separate autoencoder was trained for each month's data to capture a compressed version of customer purchase patterns. These encoded features then served as input for clustering. To find the best number of clusters, silhouette analysis was run across K values from 2 to 7. The value that produced the highest silhouette score was chosen as the optimal K. With that in place, MiniBatch K-Means was applied to group the encoded data. Clustering performance was assessed using the Silhouette Score to gauge how well the groups were separated. [37]; the Calinski-Harabasz Index, which assesses cluster compactness [39]; and the Davies-Bouldin Index, which evaluates the distinctiveness of clusters [40].

Clustering results for April show five distinct customer segments shaped by age, gender, and buying behavior. Silhouette analysis identified five as the optimal number of clusters, with a silhouette score of 0.4818, suggesting moderate separation. The Calinski-Harabasz Index of 8173.4351 and Davies-Bouldin Index of 0.7738 support the clustering quality.

Each group reflects a different pattern. Cluster 0 is made up entirely of young customers with a varied shopping profile, purchasing items like meat (20%), soft drinks (26%), and noodles (24%). Their habits suggest an exploratory approach to buying. Cluster 1 skews older, with 58% older adults and 42% late middle-aged. Their focus is on staples, mainly eggs (57%) and noodles (16%), showing a more routine, needs-based pattern.

Cluster 2 includes only the oldest customers, all of whom buy eggs exclusively. This points to a highly specialized, consistent habit. Cluster 3 combines young (55%) and early middle-aged (45%) shoppers who stick to quick, simple items, especially noodles (16%), indicating limited variety. Cluster 4 stands out as the most mixed, with early middle-aged (50%) and late middle-aged (45%) buyers. Their behavior blends staples and convenience foods, with purchases spread across noodles (26%), soft drinks (23%), and eggs (20%). Table 3 presents the cluster composition for April.

Table 3. Cluster Formed in April

Cluster	Dominant Age Group	Key Products
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0	Young (100%)	Meat (20%), Soft Drink (26%), Noodle M (24%)
1	Older (58%), Late Middle-Aged (42%)	Egg (57%), Noodle M (16%)
2	Oldest (100%)	Egg (100%)
3	Young (55%), Early Middle-Aged (45%)	Noodle M (16%)
4	Early Middle-Aged (50%), Late Middle-Aged (45%)	Noodle M (26%), Soft Drink (23%), Egg (20%)

Cluster	Dominant Age Group	Key Products
0	Early Middle-Aged (92%)	Egg (100%)
1	Older (80%)	Noodle M (28%), Egg (50%)
2	Young (100%)	Noodle M (68%), Egg (70%)
3	Late Middle-Aged (52%), Early Middle-Aged (46%)	Noodle M (41%), Egg (25%)
4	Older (54%)	Egg (100%)
5	Young (100%)	Noodle M (14%), Egg (38%), Cooking Oil S (24%)
6	Young (100%)	Egg (100%)

For May (Month 5), which is the Ramadhan Month, the clustering analysis determined that the optimal number of clusters was seven (K=7), as identified by the silhouette analysis, achieving a silhouette score of 0.5582. The Calinski-Harabasz index was 6446.1958, and the Davies-Bouldin index was 0.6497, indicating well-defined and compact clusters. The distribution of customers across the clusters was relatively balanced, with cluster sizes ranging from 325 to 1,035 customers. Each cluster represents distinct customer groups with varying age distributions, gender compositions, and product preferences.

Table 4 presents the segmentation of customer clusters based on age groups and purchasing behavior. Cluster 0 consists of early middle-aged customers who exclusively purchase eggs, indicating a highly specialized and consistent buying pattern. Cluster 1 is mostly older customers who stick to staple items like eggs and noodles, showing consistent, needs-based buying habits. Cluster 2 is made up entirely of young shoppers who focus on noodles and eggs, hinting at a mix of trend-driven and practical choices.

Cluster 3 includes late and early middle-aged customers with more balanced behavior, buying a variety of staple foods. Cluster 4, also older customers, shows a focused pattern, purchasing only eggs, which suggests strong loyalty to a single product. Cluster 5 features young consumers with broader, more exploratory habits, buying noodles, eggs, and cooking oil. Cluster 6, another group of young customers, mirrors Cluster 4's single-product focus but within a younger age group, centered solely on eggs.

Table 4. Cluster Formed in May

The clustering analysis for Month 6 identified six distinct customer segments, with the best number of clusters (K) determined as 6, based on a Silhouette Score of 0.5182. The evaluation metrics further show that the clustering structure is well-defined, with a Calinski-Harabasz Index of 5890.3569 and a Davies-Bouldin Index of 0.6417, suggesting that the clusters are compact and well-separated.

Table 5 breaks down customer clusters by age group, product preferences, and buying habits. Clusters 0 and 4 are highly specialized, made up of customers who only purchase eggs. Cluster 0 consists of late middle-aged buyers, while Cluster 4 is entirely older adults.

Cluster 1 captures young, exploratory shoppers who mix convenience and fresh items, especially Noodle M and fruit. Cluster 2 brings together young and early middle-aged customers with a narrow focus on eggs, pointing to practical, necessity-driven behavior. Cluster 3 is mostly older and late middle-aged individuals who combine routine with some variety, mainly buying Noodle M and eggs.

Cluster 5 includes a balanced group of early and late middle-aged customers with broader habits. They purchase a wider range of staples and fresh items, like Noodle M, fruit, and eggs. These segments reveal clear differences in shopping styles and product choices across age groups.

Table 5. Cluster Formed in June

Cluster	Dominant Age Group	Key Products
0	Late Middle-Aged (100%)	Egg (100%)
1	Young (90%)	Noodle M (34%), Fruit (34%)
2	Young (64%), Early Middle-Aged (36%)	Egg (100%)
3	Older (69%), Late Middle-Aged (31%)	Noodle M (37%), Egg (63%)
4	Older (100%)	Egg (100%)
5	Early Middle-Aged (50%), Late Middle-Aged (42%)	Noodle M (42%), Fruit (37%), Egg (32%)

After clustering, customer transitions were analyzed to see how segment assignments shifted over time. A pivot table captured each customer's cluster for the observed months, offering a clear view of who stayed put and who moved. Month columns were renamed for easier reading.

To spot changes, the number of unique cluster assignments per customer was counted. A single assignment meant the customer stayed in the same segment. Multiple assignments indicated movement. A new column, "Changed," flagged these shifts. "Changed = False" marked stable behavior across months. "Changed = True" showed evolving patterns, suggesting a shift in how those customers shop. Additionally, common transition patterns were analyzed by extracting sequences of cluster assignments for each customer across months. The frequency of these transition patterns was evaluated to identify dominant trends, such as stable customer behaviors versus shifting preferences.

Table 6. Sample of Customer Segment Transition

ID	Month 4	Month 5	Month 6	Changed
1126	3	-	-	FALSE
1127	-	-	-	FALSE
1128	-	-	1	FALSE
1129	-	1	-	FALSE
1130	4	4	0	TRUE

Table 6 shows provides sample of the customer cluster transition that track how customers' cluster

assignments change over the analyzed months (Month_4, Month_5, and Month_6). Each row represents an individual customer, identified by MEMBER_ID, and their respective cluster assignments for each month. The Changed column indicates whether a customer remained in the same cluster or transitioned to a different one.

Table 7. Common Transition Patterns All

Month 4	Month 5	Month 6	Frequency
4	-	-	532
1	-	-	320
-	-	5	281
0	-	-	272
-	3	-	232

Table 7 shows the five most frequent transition patterns in customer segmentation. The highest occurrence is customers staying in Cluster 4 in Month 4 without any recorded transitions in subsequent months (532 cases). Similarly, many customers remained in Cluster 1 (320 cases) or Cluster 0 (272 cases) without transitioning. A significant number of customers entered Cluster 5 in Month 6 (281 cases). Additionally, 232 customers appeared in Cluster 3 in Month 5 without data for other months. These patterns indicate stability in certain customer segments while also highlighting shifts in purchasing behavior.

The transition patterns observed in the dataset strongly suggest a seasonal purchasing behavior, particularly influenced by Ramadhan (Month 5). The fact that many customers transition from no transaction to an active cluster in Month 5 and then back to no transaction in Month 6 indicates that Ramadhan plays a significant role in driving purchases. During Ramadhan (Month 5), customer engagement increased significantly, with many previously inactive customers making purchases, likely due to heightened food consumption and preparation needs. Staples such as eggs, noodles, and cooking essentials were in high demand. However, in Month 6, transactions dropped, as many customers who were active in Ramadhan did not continue purchasing, reflecting a bulk-buying behavior ahead of Eid celebrations. Additionally, Ramadhan attracted new or seasonal buyers, possibly driven by promotions and bulk purchasing for family gatherings.

Table 8. Transition Patterns For Change = True

Month 4	Month 5	Month 6	Frequency
4	3	5	120
4	3	-	116
4	-	5	80
0	-	1	59
1	1	3	54
-	3	5	51
1	4	-	48
0	5	-	39
3	0	2	39
3	6	2	37

Table 8 presents the most common transitions among customers whose purchasing behavior changed across the observed months (Change = True). The most frequent transition pattern (4 → 3 → 5) occurred 120 times, suggesting a shift in customer preferences before and after Ramadhan. Additionally, many transitions involved customers moving from a transactional state to "No Transaction" in subsequent months, indicating seasonal purchasing behavior, where buyers engaged more in Month 5 (Ramadhan) but reduced their activity afterward. The presence of movements such as (0 → - → 1) and (3 → 6 → 2) also suggests that some customers experimented with different product clusters over time.

Customer habits shift during and after Ramadan, and these changes show up in how people move between clusters. Each cluster represents a different group with its own buying patterns, shaped by age, shopping habits, and seasonal trends. One major shift was from Cluster 4 in Month 4 to Cluster 3 in Month 5, then to Cluster 5 in Month 6. In Month 4, these customers, mostly middle-aged bought a mix of staples and convenience foods like noodles (26%), soft drinks (23%), and eggs (20%). By Ramadan in Month 5, many moved to Cluster 3, buying more staples like noodles (41%) and eggs (25%) for quick meal prep. After Ramadan, they transitioned to Cluster 5, adding fresh produce like fruit (37%) back into their diets.

Another shift involved Cluster 0 in Month 4, made up of young consumers who experimented with purchases, including meat (20%), soft drinks (26%),

and noodles (24%). Many stopped shopping in Month 5, likely because students and single buyers relied more on family meals or community iftars. By Month 6, they reappeared in Cluster 1, favoring healthier foods like fruit (34%) and noodles (34%), suggesting a post-Ramadan diet adjustment.

Cluster 1 in Month 4, mostly older and middle-aged shoppers who preferred staples like eggs (57%) and noodles (16%), saw many move to Cluster 3 in Month 5. The pattern points to stockpiling before Ramadan. By Month 6, many had stopped buying altogether, likely because their needs were already met.

Some customers kept steady habits. Cluster 2 in Month 4 was made up entirely of older shoppers who only bought eggs. They stayed in this group through Ramadan and after, showing a consistent, need-based approach to shopping.

an observable change is in Cluster 3 in the 4th month where the Cluster mostly consists of young and early middle age customers where these consumers have a tendency to buy noodles. In the fifth month, many consumers switched from Cluster 0, where egg purchases were very dominant in this Cluster, then consumers in this Cluster switched to basic needs during the month of Ramadan. In the sixth month, most of them then changed again, this time to Cluster 2, where consumers in this Cluster tried to maintain their focus on essential products such as eggs and remained there until Ramadan left.

Cluster 5 in the 4th month showed more varied changes with young consumers purchasing egg noodles and cooking oil. The following month consumers in this Cluster switched to Cluster 6 where eggs were the only purchase that continued to be purchased. Furthermore, most of this group in the sixth month also ended up in Cluster 2, this shows a continuous preference for basic needs products rather than returning to the previous pattern, namely a more varied learning pattern.

These movements show how a major event like the month of Ramadan can influence consumer behavior. At the beginning of the fasting month, consumers tend to buy to stock up early so that consumers focus more on basic needs during the fasting month, then gradually consumers begin to adapt when the fasting month ends. For businesses this provides an opportunity to better adapt to seasonal events or seasonal campaigns and maintain engagement after the peak period. These changes also show how food choices evolve across consumer segments in response to cultural and seasonal events.

• Pre-Ramadan Stocking Boosts Sales

Before the fasting month of Ramadan, sales generally increase in the first week because consumers start to stock up on essential daily products. This can be seen from the high consumer demand for products such as eggs, noodles and cooking oil, where this demand is driven by the desire to prepare for the fasting month with the family. The increase in early Ramadan sales reflects cultural and practical routines in society such as avoiding price increases at the end of the day or running out of products. For businesses, this pattern creates a clear window of opportunity. For businesses, this type of pattern provides a very good opportunity where businesses can provide discounts when consumers shop in large quantities, or promotions for those who buy early, or various packages that are needed during the fasting month. Placing various promotions during this period can change consumer behavior to be more forward, reduce supply pressure during peak days, and increase overall revenue by aligning with how people actually shop during the season.

• Post-Ramadan Sales Drop and Retention Challenges

In June, there was a clear decline in sales. This was most likely due to many consumers having already stocked up in preparation for Ramadan. The urge to make purchases that was previously seen in the first week is now starting to disappear so that daily transactions are also decreasing. For the company, this change is a sign of a difficult transition period. After the peak sales have passed, maintaining consumer interest in shopping becomes more difficult, especially when consumers feel that their needs have been met. To overcome this decline, the company can provide a strategy after Ramadan that can maintain engagement more than during the fasting period. Targeted discounts on non-staple items, loyalty rewards for repeat purchases, or personalized offers based on past behavior can help sustain momentum. These approaches not only encourage continued spending but also strengthen the customer relationship during what might otherwise be a quiet stretch.

• Ramadan Brings in New Shoppers

Some customers only shop during Ramadan, as seen in the (No Transaction → 3 → 5) transition. Special promotions and family bundles can attract these buyers. However, without follow-up engagement, they may not return. Personalized offers and post-Ramadan incentives can turn seasonal shoppers into long-term customers.

• Changing Food Priorities

During Ramadan, people focus on staple foods, but after fasting, many shift back to fresh produce. Young shoppers, in particular, return to a more varied diet. Marketing should reflect this by emphasizing staple foods before and during Ramadan, then shifting to health-focused messaging afterward.

• Timing Promotions in Phases

This study shows that customer segmentation isn't static but it shifts with seasons, cultural events, and external influences. Ramadan is a strong example, but the same principle applies to other shopping cycles. The data suggests a three-phase marketing approach:

- Pre-Ramadan (Month 4): Offer bulk-buying incentives for staple foods. Membership discounts can encourage early purchases.
- During Ramadan (Month 5): Focus on easy-to-prepare meals and high-energy foods. Ramadan-exclusive bundles and meal kits can attract buyers.
- Post-Ramadan (Month 6): Promote fresh produce and healthy options. Loyalty programs and exclusive discounts can keep customers engaged.

People don't fit into fixed categories. Customer behavior tends to shift with outside influences things like promotions, financial stress, or cultural events. Spotting these triggers early gives businesses a chance to act, instead of reacting too late. This is where transition-based segmentation comes in. Rather than locking customers into fixed groups, it tracks how they move between behavioral states as their needs or context change. changes driven by economic changes or holidays or perhaps marketing campaigns can be detected and anticipated so that they are not only analyzed after the fact.

With artificial intelligence, this process can be accelerated and can be more accurate. Machine learning can flag changes that are not so big early on, then predict where consumers will go and can organize campaigns before the changes actually occur. The ability to respond to changes in real time in a fast-moving market is an advantage where businesses that are able to continue to follow these behavioral changes will continue to survive. The rest risk falling behind [41].

4.1 Implications

The results of this study show that customer purchasing behavior is not fixed but shifts in response to cultural, seasonal, and situational

factors. For instance, a clear change occurs between the increased spending seen during Ramadan and the reduced activity that follows. These patterns suggest that customer value is time-sensitive and context-dependent. Businesses that continue to rely on static customer relationship models may fail to respond effectively to these changes. Our segmentation approach addresses this issue by predicting behavior based on recent trends, allowing businesses to adjust promotions, manage inventory, and re-engage customers more effectively.

The model can be integrated into a business intelligence dashboard and applied directly within retail environments. For example, a grocery store could connect it to its point-of-sale system and use monthly updates from autoencoder-based clustering to track how customer groups change over time. Marketing teams could then use this information to identify which customer segments respond most to promotions during specific events and tailor their offers accordingly. Since the method relies only on standard POS and membership data, it remains accessible to small and medium-sized retailers, not just large-scale e-commerce firms.

5. CONCLUSION

Traditional segmentation methods, whether based on demographics, location, or past behavior tend to assume that customer preferences stay the same. The findings in this study challenge that assumption. Segments shift over time, shaped by seasonal changes, cultural moments, and shifts in the economy. With AI-driven adaptive segmentation, machine learning models can track these movements as they happen. Instead of locking customers into fixed categories, real-time data shows how behavior changes in response to immediate needs. Transition patterns reveal how customers move between groups, exposing the rigidity of conventional models. AI helps businesses spot these shifts early, making space for predictive analytics, targeted messaging, and more responsive strategies.

The results underline the need to rethink static segmentation. Adopting AI-based approaches allows businesses to keep pace with evolving behavior, build stronger customer relationships, and stay competitive in a market where change is constant. That said, the dataset used in this study focuses only on staple and convenience goods, limiting the range of consumer behavior captured. The three-month window also highlights short-term shifts but leaves long-term patterns unexplored.

Future research should look beyond seasonal cycles, examining how factors like inflation, policy changes, or supply chain issues affect segmentation. Adding real-time signals such as sentiment or digital activity could also improve prediction and deepen behavioral insights.

The model presented in this study works well in retail settings but depends on the availability of reliable transaction and demographic data, which may not always be accessible. It also operates on a monthly time scale, which could overlook more subtle, short-term changes in behavior. The use of MiniBatch K-Means assumes that customer groups form roughly spherical clusters, a condition that may not reflect the complexity of actual consumer patterns. In addition, the analysis is limited to staple goods, so the findings may not apply to sectors such as luxury products or services.

This study focuses on short-term shifts in consumer behavior. Future research could extend this work by examining longer-term trends, such as changes in brand loyalty, customer attrition, or responses to broader forces like inflation or increased digital adoption. Incorporating sentiment data from sources like social media or product reviews could also help capture the emotional drivers behind consumer decisions. Finally, comparing this approach with other real-time clustering techniques, such as HDBSCAN or online DBSCAN, may reveal performance differences in more complex or noisy retail environments.

Open Data Statement

The dataset used in this study is business-sensitive and contains financial and customer information, and therefore cannot be shared publicly. Access may be granted upon request for academic purposes, subject to confidentiality approval.

Ivan Diryana Sudirman: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing; Original Draft, Formal Analysis, Visualization, Project Administration.

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